

ORION | Trapezium

A Monthly Publication of the ORION Astronomical Society

UCAC4 331-100198

This is the field of g-magnitude 13.6 star UCAC4 331-100198 (indicated by red dashes) in SE Ophiuchus, imaged at TAO. This star was predicted soon to be occulted by the 16.2 magnitude main-belt asteroid 621 Werdandi, at 01:25:56 am Eastern, Sat 21 Jun 2025. This stack of 125 4-sec frames was captured by Ted Barnes from 1:07-1:15 am Eastern, using a QHY174MGPS camera attached to a 20 cm Orion Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph. Our attempts to extract information regarding the occultation of this faint star have been successful, using a modified stacking approach. For more information see the discussions in this issue.

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Page Three Astronomy

Imaging anomaly from June 20, 2025 (satellite, meteor??) – each frame is a 60 second exposure

Frames before and after frame on right

Frame with lines and strange light bursts

Lines in the Sky

Don Spong has a habit of recording interesting linear features or trails of uncertain origin in the sky. During the recent Dark Stargaze of 20 Jun 2025 he recorded two approximately parallel lines with associated flashes in a galaxy field in Northeastern Virgo. If you would like to submit your opinions, measurements and / or analyses regarding the origins of these lines and flashes (planes, missiles, BEMs, Musk, usw.), we will be happy to include your comments in the next issue.

The **ORION Astronomical Society** is a science and astronomy group founded in April 1974 by scientists from the United States Department of Energy facilities at Oak Ridge, Tennessee. We primarily serve the communities of Oak Ridge and Knoxville and the counties of Anderson, Knox, and Roane.

ORION's mission is to support scientific research, teaching, and astronomical activities in East Tennessee. We hold monthly public meetings at the Oak Ridge RSCC Campus, and are active at Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO), hosting public events, sharing knowledge of the skies, and helping to provide intellectually stimulating programs. ORION works to share the wonders of the cosmos and the culture of science.

ORION members include scientists, engineers, technicians, IT experts, artists, students, and others with varied talents and expertise. Over half of ORION members own telescopes, many are amateur radio operators, and some have expertise in astrophotography.

ORION has working relationships with several organizations, including museums and other amateur astronomy groups. Membership is open to individuals who will actively contribute their time and ideas. The annual membership fee is \$20, and student discounts are available. There is no charge for our newsletters and publications, or for participation in most ORION activities.

ORION Board and Officers:

President: Don Spong

VP and Program Chair: David Fields

Social Chair: Noah Frere

Secretary: Rob Fowler

Treasurer: Bob Edwards

Editor quondam: Ted Barnes

Astrotechnologist: Rob Scott

Videographer: Rob Fowler

Obed Site Outreach: Joshua Gray.

TRAPEZIUM is a monthly publication of the ORION Astronomical Society. The issue date is the Friday preceding the monthly ORION meeting, chosen to provide timely information regarding the planned Program.

From March 2025 we will be working towards issuing a somewhat shorter version of the Trapezium, which will still include important information regarding the monthly ORION presentation, as well as dates and other information regarding Public Stargazes and other notable events relating to ORION and TAO.

Regarding the contents of this revised Trapezium, we have already concluded that some components, such as a separate Astrophotography section, are so important for a publication on amateur astronomy that one really cannot justify excluding them.

Messages from ORION

This has been quite a spectacular month in astronomy, with the recent release of the first seven days of results from the new Vera Rubin telescope in Chile. Construction of this large telescope (8.4 meter) has been underway for 15 years. It is able to image the whole sky every 3 days for at least the next 10 years, and it's predicted that it will identify 20 billion new objects, including 10 million new moving objects. So far it has identified 2,104 new asteroids, based on just looking at 1% of the sky. Vera Rubin takes the place of the earlier Sloan Sky survey telescope (2.5 meter), and will offer much higher resolution and light gathering capability. It is expected that in the next year it will find more new asteroids than were discovered in the last 200 years. If all of this makes you despair of doing your own astrophotography (not me yet), then I have heard about several citizen science projects that are starting up to analyze the massive amounts of new data from Vera Rubin. One involves looking for objects with comet tails. Another called the "galaxy zoo" will use volunteers to classify galaxy shapes. There will likely be other opportunities to get involved as the project moves forward.

This July the new moon is on July 24, with July 26-27 being a good dark sky weekend. The full moon (known as the Buck moon) is July 10. There will not be much opportunity for planets, except for Mars and Mercury in the early evening and Venus in early morning. There are two meteor showers on July 29-30, the Southern Delta Aquarids and the Alpha Capricornids; fortunately the moon will be minimal during these showers. Another object to watch for beginning in mid-July is the ISS (International Space Station). It will be visible most nights, and in some places one can see it pass over twice in one night. With respect to deep space objects, there are many opportunities in July. A few are: NGC 6210 (the Turtle Nebula), 5400 ly away in the constellation Hercules; M57 (the Ring Nebula) in Lyra, 2500 ly away; M13 (Globular Cluster in Hercules), 22 kly away (look for the propeller shape region near the center); M8 (Lagoon Nebula) and M20 (Trifid Nebula) in the constellation Hercules, 4100 ly away; M17 (the Swan Nebula) 5000 ly away in the constellation Sagittarius; and NGC 6543 (the Cat's Eye nebula), 3300 ly away in the constellation Draco. There are also many interesting objects in the constellation Cygnus (Eastern and Western Veil Nebulae, the Wild Duck Cluster, etc.). Finally, this is the season to be observing and imaging the Milky Way, if you can get to a good dark site.

President's Message (cont.)

As noted elsewhere in the Journal (Page Three Astronomy), I picked up some unusual satellite (airplane?) tracks in my imaging on June 20. This is likely to become more common; from the research I've done I find that Starlink now has 7,900 satellites in orbit, and expects to add 12,000 to 34,000 more. Most satellites pass over in the direction they were launched, West to East, but there are some specialized satellites (military surveillance and weather) that are on North-South trajectories.

Observatory Way

July 2025

The photo on the left shows our new road sign for the Roane State Tamke Allan Observatory. Traveling west, the sign is on the left as you turn into Observatory Way from Caney Creek Road, just past Joiner Hollow Road.

TAO Public Stargazes and Special Events

TAO offers Public Stargazes to the community on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month, weather permitting. Our usual schedule for the summer is to open at 8:30 pm and continue to nominally 10:30 pm -- later when the sky and attendance encourage this. Opening time changes according to the season, and a good guide is to arrive at the observatory about sunset, when weather is encouraging. These stargazes are supported by local astronomy clubs, especially ORION members and friends, and benefit our students and community. Our TAO stargazes are usually well-attended, with a full classroom of visitors for evening astronomy lectures.

The last half of July offers the following attractions:

July 16: Most TAO astronomers will attend our Monthly (3rd Wednesday) ORION meeting at the Oak Ridge RSCC Campus.

July 19: Our "Third Saturday" **TAO Public Stargaze** offers (weather permitting) an opportunity to open up to the public and show some dark and beautiful skies.

July 20: Once again, the waning crescent moon wades through the Pleiades star cluster in the hours before dawn in the east. Look for earthshine on the moon. Get your binoculars, smartphones and cameras ready.

July 21: The waning slim crescent moon in the east-northeast before dawn is above the beautiful and bright Venus, all in the lovely constellation of Taurus the Bull. Look for earthshine on the moon.

July 22: The waning and very slim crescent moon is in the east-southeast before dawn below and to the left of Venus. Jupiter joins this sky sight in the predawn sky. Look for earthshine.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

July 22-23: Late evening to predawn. If we are fortunate enough to have clear skies soon after midnight on Tue-Wed 22-23 July, we will likely attempt to observe and capture an **asteroid occultation** in the constellation Aquarius, in which the 16th magnitude asteroid 1776 Kuiper will occult (eclipse) an 11th magnitude star in the Southeast, at 00:38 am Eastern, Wed 23 Jul 2025. Max duration 4.2 secs, predicted event center time 04:38:18 UT. No Moon! Join us and win a dark star for your lapel.

July 23: The waning and very slim crescent moon joins Jupiter in the east-southeast before dawn, both below and to the left of Venus. This sky sight in the predawn sky and binoculars will help the view. Look for earthshine.

July 26: The waxing crescent moon in the west at dusk joins Regulus in a close conjunction. You need to look as soon as twilight fades. Look for earthshine on the moon.

July 28: The waxing crescent moon is in the west at dusk close to Mars. Look for earthshine on the moon.

July 29-30: The Delta Aquarids meteor shower will be best seen after midnight toward dawn. Be sure to view the video to get some tips for watching meteor showers. Link: <https://earthsky.org/astronomy-essentials/everything-you-need-to-know-delta-aquarid-meteor-shower/>

July 30: The star Spica and the almost first quarter moon pair up in the Southwest as it grows dark.

TAO Astronomers support our Astronomy Classes, our Public Stargazes, and our Special Events. Examples of special events are eclipses, planetary transits across the sun, and Asteroid Occultations. A recurring special event is our monthly “International Friendship Stargaze” which is held during the week of the first quarter moon at the Bissell Park “International Friendship Bell” in Oak Ridge.” The last week in August ushers in a 1st Quarter moon, and an opportunity for an International Friendship Stargaze” so we can add that to our calendar:

Many of our events are highly successful, but we avoid inclement and dangerous weather conditions. Working around the weather challenges of East Tennessee proves interesting.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

June 20 TAO Stargaze

Our second stargaze of each month corresponds to the new moon and thus has become a “dark sky” stargaze. Setup began at sunset for this truly enjoyable stargaze. Here's an aerial photo from astronomer/drone pilot Don Spong.

Don also took some interesting astrophotos, with (as usual) some intrusions from interesting aerial craft. Those shown as lines on the photos (following page) are probably satellites, but their flashing was unusual, and promoted considerable discussion.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

Imaging anomaly from June 20, 2025 (satellite, meteor??) – each frame is a 60 second exposure

Frames before and after frame on right

Frame with lines and strange light bursts

See also the “Page Three Astronomy” regarding these images.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

July 03 International Friendship Stargaze

Each month we offer a first-quarter moon urban stargaze in the spirit of International Friendship. We had an excellent evening on August 3, attended by a couple of groups of guest stargazers, as well as astronomers Alex, Ayala, Rob, Ted, and David. Most of us, both guests and astronomers, participated in striking the International Friendship Bell.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

July 05 TAO Public Stargaze

The skies were not the best, since we had a summer haze, and the evening moon was brighter than we might like. It's better not to complain though.

We had *ca.* 12 visitors for this event, and provided astronomy lectures by Don and David in the classroom, which received many good questions.

Rob and David worked with the Meade LX-200 telescope (with our CGE Celestron mount), testing its power use and positional accuracy during several processes. In the following figure, the initial setting was a hardware home (HH). We first aligned on Arcturus, then added Antares and Altair. This was followed by extensive GoTo operation testing, then finishing by doing a software home (SH) position set, followed by final GoTo testing. A hand control paddle (HC) was used for all these tests.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

July 05 TAO Public Stargaze (cont.)

Power drain was nominal throughout testing, with quiescent power about 0.25A, power with one motor about .7A, and with two motors, about .9A. Voltage remained nominally about 12.1V during all operations using the 1.5A Celestron power supply.

We concluded that our Meade microswitch replacement and lubrication had been successful, and the Meade was operating well with the HC. The possibility remains that there were some electrical transients, since the in-line voltage and current meters had a response time of about a second.

New Oak Ridge Library Displays

The Oak Ridge Public Library has asked us to leave up our astronomy displays for another month! So stop by the Library and enjoy them! The first Display accents some of the adventures offered by astronomy as one follows challenges and progress over a wide span of human history.

The display offers several historically important astronomy books, a small telescope (excellent for beginners), an "Eggclipse" Astronomy Egg that commemorates our 2024 solar eclipse; an early barometer, and some other astronomical and calculating instruments.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

This second library display focuses more on photographic challenges and discoveries, and what amateur astronomers may find in the skies.

Other offerings in display #2 are a second small (reflecting) telescope; an ORION 50th anniversary T-Shirt that also commemorates our recent solar eclipse; and some solar filters that were designed by local astronomers, assembled by our TAO astronomy students, and given to participants at our TAO planetary occultation observations.

The displays were assembled by teams of astronomers from ORION and TAO.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

Astrospheric PRO Status now available for ORION and TAO astronomers

Over the past 5 years most astronomers have appreciated the usefulness of Astrospheric (www dot astrospheric dot com). The program is now available on our TAO website www dot roanestate dot edu / obs) and as free apps for Android and iPhone devices. For those astronomers wanting personalized access to Astrospheric, ORION has recently achieved Pro membership for the group, and makes Pro membership in Astrospheric available to TAO astronomers. Anyone wishing to avail themselves of this opportunity can follow these instructions:

Register with Astrospheric for a free account. I use the iPhone app and usually login to www dot astrospheric dot com .

Next, from the **Astrospheric** home page on an iPhone, Android, or browser, do this:

- + ensure you're logged into your Astrospheric account
- + click the little sparkling **S** at the upper right of the screen to enter the Subspace section;
- + select JOIN GROUP and select Oak Ridge Isochronous Observation Network (ORION);
- then
- + request membership.

When your request is processed, you'll become a PRO member of Astrospheric.

ORION Board Meetings ElCantarito

- Rob Fowler

This is a summary of topics discussed recently at the weekly (Monday 1 pm) ORION Board Meeting held as a regular working lunch at ElCantarito restaurant in Oak Ridge. Notes as contributed in Stardate format by Sec. Rob Fowler.

Stardate 2025.03.31

In attendance were Robert Fowler, Ted Barnes, David Fields, Art Alison and Don Spong.
Discussed delays on new dome report due to committee participant availability.
Discussed possible going to TAO Tuesday night.
Discussed next speaker is not firm for April's meeting.
Discussed voting for officers at the next ORION Meeting.
Discussed the next Friendship Stargaze and date for same, 8th possibly.
Discussed possibly coming up with cloudy night entertainment for Friendship stargaze.
Discussed Wordsworth poem about telescopes.
Discussed potential security cams for TAO.

Stardate 2025.04.07

In attendance were David Fields, Art Alison, Ted Barnes and Rob Fowler.
Ted discussed the data acquired from his Arduino/LED test .
David discussed a mount having the ability to track asteroids via PHD2.
David discussed the Friendship Stargaze is 7:30pm Tuesday.
Discussed needing pics of new concrete pads at TAO.

Stardate 2025.04.14

In attendance were David, Ted, Art and Rob.
Ted discussed results of the Zwetana #785 occultation. After a long and dramatic story, Ted revealed a successful capture.
Noah is reaching out to Joe Baldwin about next month's presentation.
Ted discussed quantum field theory using functional methods.

Stardate: 2025.04.21

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison, Noah Frere and Rob Fowler.
Ted discussed how to use AnyDesk and log in unattended.
Ted Discussed a planetary occultation, Mars vs a 9th magnitude star on May 6th at 1 am.
David discussed progress he is making with a Meshtastic receiver.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.04.21 (cont.)

Mentioned 4 visitors who showed up at TAO and new member Kevin Wilson.

David brought up calendar access .

Discussed problem with rotation of glow dome lid. Watch for migration of wheel axels.

One axle migrated in and caused the lid to bind.

Stardate: 2025.04.28

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison, Kevin Wilson, John Cliff and Rob Fowler.

Briefly mentioned domes on CloudyNights.com.

Discussed Upcoming Mars/Star occultation and relevant challenges.

HD 74058 vs Mars just after midnight 00:44 night 5th/6th morn.

TAO Stargaze beginning at May 3rd 8pm.

Friendship Stargaze possibly May 6th.

Briefly discussed avoiding Feynman's van.

Shared astrophotos.

Discussed potentially going to TAO tonight & Noah's class.

Stardate: 2025.05.05

In attendance were David Fields, Art Alison, Ted Barnes, Kevin Wilson, and Rob Fowler.

David asked if we have a set program for May. That remains unclear. Ted contacted Noah to confirm. We await a reply.

Ted mentioned the next annual IOTA meeting is possibly going to be in New Mexico in Oct.

Stardate: 2025.05.12

At 11am David, Ted & Art met at the Library and made a first pass as setting up a display case for the club. Rob joined later. It was artistically done, decorated with a small telescope, some antique books, and astrophotos.

Discussed whether Kevin might give the May lecture and what topics he has ready. He agreed to speak on the topic of stellar spectroscopy. Ted mentioned the next possible occultation on the early morning on 5/21/2025.

Stardate: 2025.05.19

In attendance were Don, David, Ted, Art, Kevin, and Rob.

Kevin brought up Benjamin Baniker as a potential lecturer.

Rob announced that the most recent lecture is on YouTube.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Star Date: 2025.05.26

In attendance were Don, Dave, Art & Rob.

David suggested improvement's to the Meade's power supply in hopes of reducing noise, higher amperage power supply, adding ferrite cores.

Dave discussed getting a construction party to begin construction on the Dob shelter.

Discussed parking issues at TAO.

Star Date: 2025.06.02

In attendance were Don, David, Bob, Art, Juan, Kevin and Noah (and Sunny).

We met early at the library to discuss the current and new display box. Discussed meeting again, tomorrow (Tuesday).

David suggested Wednesday night 8:30pm as the next Friendship Stargaze.

Kevin suggested meeting at TAO to look at the Meade's encoder.

Noah suggested reaching out to Gareth Davis to see if he has any potential acquaintances for another lecture.

Don asked about the new dome project.

David responded with a tale of woe regarding the Roane purchasing project.

Star Date: 2025.06.09

In attendance were Don, David, Art and Rob (joined by John Rather).

David purchased 2 coin cells for the Celestron CGM mount.

He also purchased a few ferrite cores to suppress noise from the power supply.

Ted expressed an interest in having help with this months Trapezium.

Discussed the new optical telescope coming online in the Atacama Desert.

Briefly mentioned the library displays and Oak Ridge street lighting.

Noah mentioned that Gareth Davis can give the next lecture.

Star Date: 2025.06.16

In attendance were Don, Kevin, Art and Rob.

Rob showed his submission for the AMSE poster.

Kevin & Don discussed PixInsight.

We confirmed Kevin is speaking this month.

Kevin discussed the Astronomical League and it's various programs, contests for various achievements.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Star Date: 2025.06.23

Due to crowding at the table, no notes were taken.

In attendance were Don, David, Ted, Art, Kevin and Robert.

Star Date: 2025.06.30

In attendance were David, Ted, Art, Kevin, and Rob. Don sat in for a short while.

Ted & Rob discussed results of the occultation via a new process.

Kevin presented a new ORION Logo.

Kevin announced he will be moving out of the immediate area.

David presented Kevin with a gift ORION T-Shirt.

David brought up shop type measurements he intends to do on the Meade.

The group went on discuss various theoretical topics.

Mentioned 4 visitors who showed up at TAO and new member Kevin Wilson

David brought up calendar access

Discussed problem with rotation of glow dome lid.

Watch for migration of wheel axels. One axel migrated in and caused the lid to bind.

Star Date: 2025.07.07

In attendance were Don, Ted, David, Art, Rob and visitor John Rather.

Conversations opened with Ted discussing digitizing the occultation substacking project.

David discussed a lightstrip project and possible application in the dome.

Ted collected info for this month's Trapezium.

David discussed attendance at the Sat July 5 Public Star Gaze, was 12, give or take.

David discussed the testing we did on the Meade and saw no alignment errors.

ORION Monthly Meetings

ORION Monthly Meeting Format

Meeting Venue: City Room (A-111), just inside the main entrance, Coffey/McNalley Bldg., Oak Ridge Campus, Roane State Community College.

7:00 pm Eastern, 3rd Wednesday of each month.

Our monthly meetings (except for December, a dinner) generally proceed as follows:

- Welcome
- Announcements
- Invited Presentation and Discussion
- Awarding of the Mug
- Astrophotography / Special Presentations

The nominal start time is 7:00 pm Eastern, on the 3rd Wednesday of the month. The beginning of the meeting will usually include announcements of general interest.

Meetings typically continue until around 9:00 pm. Please plan to stay until the end. Hopefully we will all enjoy the astrophotography and other special topics discussed in the latter part of the meeting.

Remote Viewing: A live Zoom session will usually be open during the ORION Monthly Meeting, at the link:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/88528735960?pwd=KzY4bnBHcjlhTzg3L3pOcjY0TFovUT09> or
<https://bit.ly/42apGxX>

Meeting ID: 885 2873 5960 Passcode: 716689

Title: Asteroid Occultations**Speaker: Ted Barnes****Abstract:**

In this presentation I will discuss the relatively recent topic of asteroid occultation observations by amateur astronomers. I will explain how this is done, what can be learned, why this is such an exciting activity, and how ORION is currently participating, since our first occultation at TAO in Oct 2023. Finally, I will suggest how we might contribute to new developments in asteroid research at TAO in future.

Title: Asteroid Occultations

Speaker: Ted Barnes

Mini Bio:

Ted Barnes' career as an amateur astronomer started around age 5 when he discovered the "Little Big Dipper," now better known as the Pleiades. His Barnes family resided in North Kansas City from a very early 1825; some of his early paternal and maternal ancestors lived in Anderson and Roane Counties from the 1790s. His career in the sciences involved a BSE in Applied Physics (coherent optics) from Ann Arbor, and an MS in Physics and a PhD in Theoretical Physics (1977), both from Caltech. His doctoral thesis was on the quark and gluon structure of strongly interacting particles (hadrons). After postdoctoral and research positions in Canada, Europe and the Middle East, in 1989 he accepted a position as the first Joint ORNL-UTK Collaborating Scientist. At ORNL he worked primarily on hadron physics and neutron scattering from quantum magnets, and at UTK he taught many graduate classes. He has about 150 research papers and publications in these fields. After a research career of *ca.* 35 years he moved to DOE HQ in Germantown, Maryland, where he was a Detailee and then Program Manager in the Office of Nuclear Physics. At various times he managed the national programs in Theoretical Nuclear Physics, Low Energy Nuclear Experiment, Medium Energy Experiment, Computational Nuclear Physics (SciDAC), and the National Nuclear Data Program (NNDC). Through the SciDAC program he and his DOE colleagues funded extensive collaborative programs on topics in computational nuclear astrophysics. After an NNDC review, in collaboration with other DOE Program Managers he initiated an interagency experimental component of the nuclear data program; this vital area had been inactive for about two decades. To maintain his sanity at DOE he again took up amateur astronomy, and added astrophotography. On retirement from DOE in 2018 he returned to the Oak Ridge area, where he now enjoys participating in the ORION Astronomical Society, pursuing and imaging asteroids.

ORION Last Month

Ancient Mesopotamian Astronomical Texts - *Kevin Wilson*

Our featured speaker for the June 2025 ORION Presentation was again new ORION member Kevin A. Wilson. Kevin is a graduate of Carson-Newman University, where he double majored in religion and political science. He went on to earn a Master's of Divinity and a Master's of Sacred Theology from Yale Divinity School, followed by a PhD in Hebrew Bible / Old Testament and Northwest Semitic Philology from the Johns Hopkins University. He has taught college in Klaipėda, Lithuania, North Andover, MA, Sewanee, TN, and Waverly, IA.

For his June 2025 ORION presentation, Kevin gave a truly fascinating discussion of the earliest recorded astronomical observations, from the Mesopotamian area, now primarily constituting Southern and Central Iraq. Kevin reminded us that writing began about 3300 BCE in Sumer, and the cuneiform tablets of dried clay familiar to many people, which are in the Akkadian language (a Semitic language, unlike Sumerian), appeared from about 2500 BCE. Much of the material Kevin discussed related to the Assyrian and Babylonian empires, from a somewhat later period, ca, 500-800 BCE.

The astronomical observations on dried clay cuneiform tablets are apparently records of observations by priests, as part of their religious duties. Observations of Venus and its position in the sky were especially popular. Kevin explained that each event in the sky had associated predictions for what would then happen on the Earth, so this work was basically a prediction service by the religious hierarchy.

Current research involves attempting to establish an accurate dating system for the tablets, based on their recorded observations. There are however complications due to their habit of inserting additional months in the calendar on occasions when needed, and the use of a complicated solar-lunar calendar system. Mistakes in recording events are also a problem. The good news is that a large number of tablets are believed to await discovery and interpretation.

This was a fascinating and remarkable story. Alas Kevin will soon be leaving the area, so this may be his last ORION presentation for some time. After we thanked him for this address, he again received a most valuable award from ORION President Don Spong as an acknowledgement of our appreciation.

ORION Last Month

Ancient Mesopotamian Astronomical Texts (cont.)

The enthusiastic audience for Kevin Wilson's ORION talk on Mesopotamian Astronomy, Wed 16 June 2025.

Events and Calendars, Sky Maps and Occultations

Star, Moon, Comet and Meteorgazing at TAO in 2025

We enthusiastically invite visitors to attend our Public Stargaze events, held at our dark-sky site, the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) near Kingston, Tennessee. These events are intended especially for visitors, so our buildings and facilities will be open, and there will be astronomy talks as well as public skywatching.

In Jan-Jun 2025 we plan to hold fixed-calendar public Stargaze events on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These weekend events are especially appropriate for families. We also hold public special events, such as a “Full Moonrise,” with associated Moon Music, and the occasional comet watch. The annual Perseid Meteor watch in mid-August is especially popular.

The precise dates of many of these events depend on the local weather conditions, and cannot be specified *definitively* long in advance. As an approximate guide, see the TAOCalendar pages following. Once a date is finalized we usually confirm it through the ORION online message site ORION astronomy@groups.io. Likely and unlikely dates for TAO events may be inferred from the weather predictions at TAO by Clear Sky Charts (cleardarksky dot com) and Astrospheric (astrospheric dot com).

Please confirm event dates before proceeding to TAO.

In view of the rather challenging approach road to TAO, “Observatory Way,” first-time visitors should plan to arrive before dark. Driving instructions are given at: <https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/visit.htm>

Some instructions follow, since people may be unfamiliar with procedures for stargazing at a dark-sky site.

ORION members are invited to arrive early with their telescopes and mounts, to prepare for evening observing and to share refreshments. Please bring a red flashlight, or a headband with a red-light option.

Visitors who wish to acquire red lights or red-light headbands for observing may find them at many commercial amateur astronomy sites, such as [https:// www dot high pointscientific dot com](https://www.highpointscientific.com). The “Lepro LE” LED Headlamp, model 3200008, available from Amazon for about \$10 (Aug. 2024) is a personal favorite. This is rechargeable and has separate red and white led buttons, with several brightness settings. A caution: For amateur astronomy, brighter lights are NOT preferred, and WHITE lights are highly discouraged. Please use only red lights while the Stargaze is in progress.

Parking is available on site; on entering TAO **stay to the right**, and *please use the parking area below and right (Southwest) of the TAO buildings and observing area, near the treeline*. And **PLEASE NO HEADLIGHTS ON SITE.**

Visitors are encouraged to interact with ORION astronomers who have set up and may be operating telescopes and other astronomical equipment. We enjoy public discussions, and regard this sharing of information as a primary goal of our organization. Visitors are welcome to coffee and other refreshments.

TAO Public Stargazing: A Note Regarding Scheduling and Access in 2025

In 2025 we will revert to an earlier schedule of having our Public Stargaze nights on every first and third Saturday. Of course this assumes good weather; if the weather is not suitable, a changed schedule will be announced on the group site [ORIONastronomy @ groups.io](mailto:ORIONastronomy@groups.io).

We decided that the previous (2024) schedule of a once-monthly Public Stargaze was insufficient, and having a Moon visible in some phase other than close to New gives our visitors an obvious and interesting object for viewing.

During Daylight Savings Time (mid-March through early November) we plan to hold our Public Stargaze events over the hours 8:00 pm - 11:00 pm. The planned Public Stargaze dates in Apr and Mar of 2025 are 5 Apr, 19 Apr, 3 May and 17 May.

If it is already dark when you arrive, please dim your headlights on the TAO grounds, follow the right branch of the access road, and park to the right of the TAO building, near the treeline.

Note: Parking in or near the elevated flat observing area at the front (East) of the TAO building is reserved for astronomers who are bringing their equipment.

Additional information for visitors may be found on the previous page and following two pages of this issue.

TAO Public Stargazes in June:

Sats 07 & 21 Jun 2025

Sat 07 Jun 2025

Sunset	8:54 pm
Civ dusk	9:24 pm
Ast dusk	10:43 pm
Moonrise	5:50 pm
Moonset*	4:14 am
	*08 Jun
Moon illum.	87%

Bright Gibbous Moon during this event.

Cancelled due to weather.

Sat 21 Jun 2025

Sunset	8:59 pm
Civ dusk	9:30 pm
Ast dusk	10:49 pm
Moonrise	2:51 am
Moonset	5:07 pm
Moon illum.	21%

No Moon during this event.

TAO Public Stargazes in July:

Sats 05 & 19 July 2025

Sat 05 Jul 2025

Sunset	8:59 pm
Civ dusk	9:29 pm
Ast dusk	10:47 pm
Moonrise	4:41 pm
Moonset*	2:45 am
	*06 Jul
Moon illum.	75%

Bright Gibbous Moon during this event.

Sat 19 Jul 2025

Sunset	8:54 pm
Civ dusk	9:23 pm
Ast dusk	10:37 pm
Moonrise	01:25 am
Moonset	4:08 pm
Moon illum.	33%

No Moon during this event.

TAO Calendars

Jan-Jun 2025; May & Jun 2025

The principle public events for visitors at TAO are the **Public Stargazes**, held at TAO during 2025 on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These are listed in the “**Public Fixed Events**” **TAO Calendar** for a six month period, currently Jan-Jun 2025. This appears on the page following.

Additional notable events will be included in monthly “**Special Events**” **TAO Calendars**. These include public events that do not have a fixed date long in advance, such as the **International Friendship Stargaze** in Oak Ridge, and special TAO events such as **Asteroid Occultations, Meteor Showers, Full Moonrises, Lunar (and other) Eclipses, Comet Watches**, and perhaps the occasional musical event.

These “Special Events” calendars for the current and subsequent months appear after the six-month “Public Fixed Events” calendar.

The facilities in the TAO buildings onsite will be open to the public during the “Public Fixed Events,” and will also usually be available when TAO is open to the public for some of the “Special Events.” **Please inquire regarding whether TAO will be open to the public for any “Special Event” you may wish to attend, since some may be restricted.** We will of course always try to accommodate enthusiastic visitors.

We recommend checking a TAO website such as **ORIONastronomy @ groups.io** before visiting, to confirm that listed events will proceed as planned; weather conditions for example may require a cancellation or change of date.

TAO Calendar Public Fixed Events

Jan-Jun 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 04 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 18 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Feb 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Feb 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Mar 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Mar 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 05 Apr 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 19 Apr 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 03 May 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 17 May 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 07 Jun 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 21 Jun 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm

These 2025 TAO Public Events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter and Spring, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAO Calendar Public Fixed Events

Jul-Dec 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 05 Jul 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	10:30 pm
Sat 19 Jul 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	10:30 pm
Sat 02 Aug 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	10:30 pm
Sat 16 Aug 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	10:30 pm
Sat 06 Sep 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 20 Sep 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 04 Oct 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 18 Oct 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Nov 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	9:00 pm
Sat 15 Nov 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	9:00 pm
Sat 06 Dec 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	9:00 pm
Sat 20 Dec 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	9:00 pm

These 2025 TAO Public Events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAOCalendar Special Events

Jun 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 07 Jun 2025		1 st Sat Public Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Wed 04 Jun 2025		International Friendship Stargaze (Oak Ridge)	9:00 pm	10:30 pm
Wed 11 Jun 2025		Full Moon 03:44 am Eastern		
Sat 21 Jun 2025		Occultation 621 Werdandi	01:25:55	01:25:57
Sat 21 Jun 2025		3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Wed 25 Jun 2025		New Moon 06:31 am Eastern		

TAOCalendar Special Events

Jul 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Thu 03 Jul 2025	★	International Friendship Stargaze (Oak Ridge)	8:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 05 Jul 2025	★	1st Sat Public Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Thu 10 Jul 2025	○	Full Moon 04:36 pm Eastern		
Sat 19 Jul 2025	★	3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Tue 23 Jul 2025	★	Occultation 1776 Kuiper	00:38:17	00:38:19
Wed 24 Jul 2025	●	New Moon 03:11 pm Eastern		

Occultation by Asteroid 621 Werdandi at TAO on 21 Jun 2025.

- Ted Barnes

Since we had completed our 10th asteroid occultation observation some time ago at TAO on 14 April 2025, through our *second* observation of an occultation involving the asteroid 785 Zwetana, after some delay and a failed attempt to observe an occultation by Mars, “Mars or Bust,” I decided that one should get back on the bicycle and attempt another occultation before forgetting how to ride it. There was a risk of getting stuck at Occ.X.

Many of the occultation predictions reported by the program Occult Watcher that would be visible at TAO in early Summer 2025 seemed problematic for various reasons, such as being far past midnight, associated with bright moonlight, too close to the horizon (atmospheric turbulence), or having target stars that were uncomfortably faint. To borrow a concept from the movie “The Right Stuff,” observers of asteroid occultations knew that there was a demon out there in the sky at about magnitude 13.5, and anyone who pursued an occultation of a star that faint or fainter would likely encounter disturbing observational problems that could lead to fatal errors, meaning that the occultation was not clearly observed. (No need to be overdramatic. These fatal errors are not fatal to humans.)

However if one doesn’t continue riding that bicycle, one can forget just how difficult it can be to extract an observation of an asteroid occultation of a star fainter than magnitude 13.5 . Thus without sufficient reconsideration I selected an OW table entry describing a future eclipse, visible at TAO, of the star UCAC4 331-100198 in SE Ophiuchus by the magnitude 16.2 asteroid 621 Werdanidi, on 6/21. (That’s a bit weird.) The “target star” is of g-magnitude **13.6**.

This rather faint target star did make me uncomfortable; my previous faintness record was a slightly fainter target star of g-mag **13.8** at TAO on the humid early morning of 1 Aug 2024. Considerable effort had been required to confirm that occultation. I had forgotten about the work involved in interpreting the observation of that earlier event. It was, in Caltech slang, “nontrivial.”

This time I anticipated a little difficulty in extracting the target star occultation from the images, but I assumed it would be feasible after post-processing.

Occultation by Asteroid 621 Werdandi

A JPL Horizons orbit diagram showing the orbit (white line) and position (white dot and label) of asteroid 621 Werdandi between Mars (red) and Jupiter (orange) at the time of the occultation, 1:25 am Eastern, Sat morning 21 Jun 2025.

Occultation by Asteroid 621 Werdandi

Prediction

Last Updated: 27/Apr/25,	Computed By: OWC
00:33 UT	Orbit Date: 09 Apr 2025
Data Sources:	(JPL#66)
Horizons/GaiaDR3	Error in time: 0.3 sec
Error (path widths): 0.020	Err. Ellipse PA: 96°
Err. Ellipse: 0.0026" x	OWC Id: 2405253
0.0003"	
Err. Basis: Known errors	

Event

From: 05:22:35 UT	To: 05:30:16 UT
Combined Mag: 12.71	Max Duration: 2.0 sec
Mag Drop (V): 2.37	Mag Drop (R): 2.33
Shadow Width: 57.0 km	Moon Phase: 24% sunlit
Solar Elong.: 170°	Moon Elong.: 132°

Target Star

Name: UCAC4 331-100198	V mag: 13.58
Constellation: Ophiuchus	R mag: 12.85
Diameter: ()	B mag: 14.14
RUWE: 0.90	Flags: Kepler ⚠
Gaia SourceId:	Gaia Flags:
4114085680387147904	RA [apmnt]: 17^h 18^m
RA [ICRS]: 17^h 17^m	57^s.1775
22^s.4113	Dec [apmnt]: -24° 01' 02".830
Dec [ICRS]: -23° 59' 20".157	

Object

Name: (621) Werdandi	Class: Main-belt Asteroid
Diameter: 28.8 ± 1.6	Diameter (augm): 15.81 mas
km (Occult)	Mag: 16.2 ⚠
Distance: 2.5117 au	Motion Dec: 0.99 "/hr
Motion RA: -27.85 "/hr	Rings: 0
Moons: 0	

Parameters relating to the approaching occultation event, extracted from the program Occult Watcher.

Occultation by Asteroid 621 Werdandi

OW Cloud

(621) Werdandi occults UCAC4 331-100198 on 21 Jun 2025

Change prediction: [default] Horizons/GaiaDR3, last upd: 27 Apr, 00:33 by OWC, orbit date: 09 Apr 2025 (JPL#66)

Tagged as: [AZevents](#) [NALowMag](#)

Path of the asteroid's shadow (R -> L) across East Tennessee. The shadow centerline (green) passed close to TAO (telescope icon on the white tangent line), making a long duration occultation more likely. Our position on the shadow profile is indicated by a black tick mark.

Occultation by Asteroid 621 Werdandi

A large scale sky chart at the time predicted for the occultation, generated using TheSkyX. Here one can see the location of the asteroid 621 Werdandi and the target star UCAC4 331-100198 against the very rich star fields in Ophiuchus, near the center of the Milky Way Galaxy. The star and asteroid are denoted by the red circle and crosshair, just right of the image center.

Occultation by Asteroid 621 Werdandi

This part of the galaxy is very rich indeed, as shown by this enlargement from the Deep Sky Survey DSS2. The target star is indicated by a purple crosshair near the center of this image. Note also the dark dust clouds evident in this part of Ophiuchus. This orientation of this image is East and North right.

6.6
HIP 84636 G3V

621 Werdandi &
UCAC4 331-100198

9.3

9.6

Although one can easily find the brighter stars in this TheSkyX image and the rich DSS2 image on the previous page, clearly TheSkyX has not attempted to duplicate the very rich field of fainter stars in this image. The inner green box is the appropriate f.o.v.

Occultation by Asteroid 621 Werdandi

Although I had arrived at a reasonably early time of just after 8:00 pm on 20 Jun 2025 to begin my work at TAO, I had made the cardinal error of planning to accomplish two major observing tasks in one evening. First, since Mars was available in the early evening, I planned to capture a series of Mars tests with different gains and exposures, using a robot SharpCap “sequencer” program I had written over the last week or two. One would just insert a filter in the camera, use the sequence program to loop through a series of exposures and gains (two nested loops), and then switch to the next folder.

This sounds straightforward, but as usual I hadn’t found the right optical connectors to link my 8” Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph to my QHY174GPS camera, allowing sufficient focus tube spacing to bring the entire system into good focus. I eventually managed this and completed my series of Mars images with 4 different filters about midnight.

Set up for a busy evening of astronomy at TAO. 9:16 pm, Fri 20 Jan 2025.

Occultation by Asteroid 621 Werdandi

During setup I encountered Richard Piety, and was happy to have the opportunity to present him with his “Dark Star Award” as a field commission for his independent observation at Norris Lake Park of the occultation by asteroid 14 Irene on 22 Mar 2025.

Richard Piety attaches his new Dark Star Award for observing the occultation by 14 Irene.

DARK STAR AWARD

*Occultation of star TYC 1892-00151-1 by 14 Irene
at NLO, 11:00:33 pm Eastern 22 Mar 2025*

Awardee: R. Piety

Occultation by Asteroid 621 Werdandi

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I switched immediately to the next task, of attempting to capture the occultation by 621 Werdandi, but I should have taken a break beforehand. Since I only had about an hour to prepare, I found that I was stressed out, and things were not working well. I was only able to swap out the optical coupling to a new one that I could use with about an hour to go, and I was finding alignment problems; the occultation would take place somewhat low in the South ($\text{Alt@Azi} = 30^\circ @ 188^\circ$), and the Meridian would actually cross the location of the event at 00:57 am Eastern, only 30 minutes before the event. No pressure.

I had previously given little thought to how best to avoid the Meridian just as the event was taking place. I approached the occultation site from the East, added (I think) an alignment star or two, and then slewed way back to the location of the target star, just on the West side of the Meridian. I then took a stack of 125 images of the target star at moderate gain and exposure (4 secs at a gain of 440), from 1:07 am - 1:15 am, to use as a reference image. (This reference image is shown at the top of the next page.) Only 12 minutes remaining. Fortunately the Plate Solve feature of SharpCap was working, and I used that to confirm that I was indeed close to the location of the event, RA 17 17 22.5 and Dec -23 59 20. Another problem was that the star fields in this location near the galactic center were very rich, so I was unable to confirm observationally that I really was in the correct field. I just had to capture and hope for the best. I was also having some trouble keeping the gps locked. The gps didn’t actually record the time on the frames until the 8th frame. Yes, everything tends to go wrong in the last half hour of an occultation observation attempt.

Occultation by Asteroid 621 Werdandi

The officially predicted midpoint was 01:25:56 am Eastern, with a maximum duration of 2.0 secs. Accordingly when we reached 01:25:50 am I pushed SharpCap's "Start Capture" pulldown "Start" button and began recording my preset 100 frames of 200ms duration, at a gain of 440. The sequence appeared to complete successfully, so as usual I next packed and returned home, to examine the frames later.

After my return home I examined the 100 raw 200msG440 frames; I found that these were ominously dark (one should always have a practice session so as to not be surprised by issues like this). Only four stars were easily visible in the raw frames, the brightest at g-magnitude 9.3 (near bottom center), and with more effort a counterclockwise loop at center right was also visible, with g-magnitudes 9.6, 10.7 and 11.6. Stars with g-mag fainter than about 12.0 were just not evident in the raw frames.

Stretching the brightness and contrast to the maximum in post processing, as I usually do (see bottom panel following page), I could identify stars down to g-mag 12.5 and a little fainter, but the target star with g-mag 13.6 was simply not clearly evident, so I wouldn't be able to say confidently when it was occulted by the asteroid by studying subsequent frames. For this reason I told the audience at my presentation at TAO the next evening (at the 21 June 2025 Public Stargaze) that my attempt to observe the asteroid occultation by 621 Werdandi on 20 June 2025 had alas been a "fail." I should probably have bumped the camera up to its maximum gain of 480, or used longer frames such as 400ms, or both. The frame setting of 200msG440 that I had used was just too conservative to bring out a target star near the demon magnitude of around **13.6**.

Although my choice of 200msG440 frames gave me raw images that were too faint to show the target star, even after enhancement, both Rob Fowler and David Fields were in my Public Stargaze talk, and they both suggested somehow adding sufficient (N) raw frames to give an observable target star. I objected that in adding frames, you would lose information about when the occultation actually took place. Rob suggested adding up different subsets of N frames so that the target star became visible, and by changing the time span covered by the subsets and comparing them, one might be able to identify the beginning and end of the occultation. Rob later wrote a program to do this (see the following article), which showed the feasibility of this procedure.

Occultation by Asteroid 621 Werdandi

A reference stack taken before the occultation 125 4-sec frames of the field of the $m_g = 13.6$ target star UCAC4 331-100198 (red tick marks) at a camera gain of 440, hence 125x4sG440. This image includes some post processing.

A single 200ms, gain-440 frame of the same field, taken a few seconds before the occultation, with extreme post processing to hopefully bring out the faint $m_g = 13.6$ target star. Note that the target star is unfortunately not evident in this single frame. So, this attempt to observe the disappearance of the target star using a sequence of enhanced-contrast frames, my usual practice, was a “fail.” A nearby g-mag 12.6 star evidently is visible, and perhaps even a 13.5, so we were at least close to success.

Occultation by Asteroid 621 Werdandi

Rob used my 100 x 200msG440 raw frames of this occultation, and first tried summing the first 10 ($N=10$), which had start times from 01:25:50.67 am to 01:25:52.47 am. (Since each raw frame is exposed for 200ms after the start time, $N=10$ summed frame no.1 actually represents an exposure from 01:25:50.67 am to 01:25:52.67 am. These were all from well before the expected occultation, so all 10 raw frames should be “bright” sources for the target star. When added, this worked; the summed frame showed the target star clearly. (See the figure on the second page of Rob’s following article.)

To generate his second summed frame no.2, Rob summed raw frames 2-11, covering the exposure period 01:25:50.87 am to 01:25:52.87 am. The target star was again visible, with similar brightness, as the occultation had not yet started.

For ease in working through these $N=10$ summed frames, Rob assembled them into a movie. One just watches the movie for the first summed frame that shows a sudden step down in brightness; this will take place when the last (and latest) of the $N=10$ summed frames encounters an extinguished target star. The first “dimmed” summed star I observed included raw frames 12-21, hence an exposure period of 01:25:52.87 am to 01:25:54.87 am. Since this sum is fainter because the last contributing frame (21) is weak, and hence includes the occulted star, we conclude that the disappearance time D was within the exposure period of frame 21, 01:25:54.67 am to 01:25:54.87 am. We assigned this disappearance to the middle of frame 21, 01:25:54.77 am, which we rounded to $D = 01:25:54.8$ am. (With $N=16$ this increases slightly to 55.0, see following pages.)

Successive summed frames show a fainter target star as more of the $N=10$ frames fall within the occultation period. We next go through a sequence of dark frames, in which all of the summed frames are within the occultation period. A glimmer of light from the target star next appears at the timestamp 01:25:57.87 secs, when the last frame recorded, exposed from 01:25:57.87 am to 01:25:58.07 am, records the end of the occultation during that period. Using the middle of the final frame and rounding as above gives us an estimated reappearance time of $R = 01:25:58.0$ am. (Also increases, to 58.2, with $N=16$.)

From D and R above we recover a duration of $R-D = 3.2$ secs and a (midpoint) event time of $(D+R)/2 = 01:25:56.4$ am. The observed event time is in excellent agreement with the predicted 01:25:56 am, but our observed duration of 3.2 secs is significantly longer than the predicted maximum of 2.0 secs. We assigned an error of ± 0.1 secs (spanning a 200ms frame) to both D and R . (With $N=16$, the estimated midpoint became 56.6.)

Occultation by Asteroid 621 Werdandi

It proved to be possible to photoelectrically time the occultation with stacked frames by simply attaching a photoresistor to an external terminal while running the stacked frame “movie” generated by Rob, with the target star image placed under the photoresistor, and then stepping through the movie and recording the resistance. An xmgrace plot of the inverse $k\Omega$ resistance vs the time of the latest frame, using summed $N=16$ frames, is shown below. The actual recording device is shown on the page following.

The initial target star disappearance is evident at 55.0 secs, where the summed frame darkens when a final frame with a dark star is first encountered. Additional dark frames darken the target star further until a frame finally brightens at reappearance, at 58.2 secs.

Occultation by Asteroid 621 Werdandi

This shows the high-tech photoresistor readout used to extract estimates of local image brightness versus time for the N=16 stacked frames, as shown in the plot on the previous page. The target star is placed under the photocell, which is covered by a quasi-opaque tape and connected to a multimeter. Then one steps through stacked image frames. Aspects of the plot can be identified with the target star disappearance and reappearance times D and R.

DIY photoresistor readout.

These N=16 estimates for D and R are

$$D = 01:25:55.0(1) \text{ am}$$
$$R = 01:25:58.2(1) \text{ am,}$$

with an estimated error of +/- 0.1 secs from +/- half a 200ms bin width. There is also a fine point, the frame timestamps tell you when the 200ms frame BEGINS to collect light, so we have displaced each timestamp by +0.1 sec in compensation.

These considerations give duration and midpoint times of

$$\text{dur} = R - D = \mathbf{3.2(2) \text{ sec,}}$$
$$\text{Event Time (Eastern)} = (R+D)/2 = \mathbf{01:25:56.6(1) \text{ am.}}$$

The midpoint is in agreement with the predicted value of the Event Time, 05:25:56 UT. Our observed duration of 3.2(2) however is considerably longer than the prediction of 2.0 secs. Note that our predicted duration error is +/- 0.2 secs.

These results were submitted to IOTA on 5 July 2025.

A Novel Approach to Processing Faint Image Sequences

- Robert G. Fowler

A few days after the 2025/6/21 occultation attempt with asteroid 621 Werdandi, Ted Barnes shared his results with a packed classroom up at the Tamke Allan Observatory. In the hours preceding the occultation, he had taken a multi-frame sequence, stacked it, and created a nice clear reference frame of the star in question. But at the time of the occultation, he took a


```
File Edit View Search Run Debug Options Tools
make_c

FOR x = 1 TO 120
  s$ = "s:\3\" + MID$(STR$(x), 2)
  MKDIR s$
NEXT x

File Edit View Search Run Debug Options
c

LET A = 1
pad$ = "00000"
FOR fil = 1 TO 100
  nam$ = MID$(STR$(fil), 2)
  n = LEN(nam$)
  nam2$ = LEFT$(pad$, 5 - n) + nam$
  FOR cpy = A TO A + 9
    s$ = "copy s:\2\pics\target_" + nam$
    SHELL s$
  NEXT cpy
  LET A = A + 1
NEXT fil
PRINT "All done."
```

sequence of much shorter raw frames, 100 frames at 200ms each. The upshot was, the shorter frames, even after brightness enhancing, did not reveal the star at all. At least, not that could be teased out from the noise of the frame. Ted declared this occultation attempt a miss.

Listening to his lecture gave me an idea. So I posed the question, “What if we stacked 10 frames and *then* tinkered with the brightness?” I had no idea whether it would work but there was a chance. The objection was raised, “if we stack 10 frames, then how will we know when the occultation happened?” My plan was to create many stacks of 10 frames each from the original 100 raw 200ms frames. The first stack could include for example summed frames 1-10, the second 2-11, and the third 3-12 and so on to 91-100. The hope was that with 10 summed frames the faint target star would be visible; and on the first summed frame that included the occultation, the target star would dim

A Novel Approach to Processing Faint Image Sequences

(10%), and that would be just enough to notice. We would then mark that as the first summed frame during the occultation. Likewise, the first summed frame in which the target star began to re-appear would mark the end of the occultation. It really was just a wild hunch. I had no idea if 10 frames at 200ms each would be enough to tease out the errant target star. But I was anxious to try.

Ted graciously offered to share his raw data and late Friday night I began to make an attempt. I started by creating 2 short BASIC programs, the first to create 100 folders, and the second to copy the frames as intended, into their stacks of 10 summed frames. I then imported the first batch of 10 into Deep Sky Stacker, a program I had little experience with. After about 30 minutes I had generated my first sum of 10 frames. Goal 1 seemed to be achieved, the target star was indeed visible, although just barely. But the time invested was enormous considering I would only have to do this over 90 more times.

The target star recovered from 10 summed 200ms frames.

A Novel Approach to Processing Faint Image Sequences

I knew there was probably a way automate this process too, now that I had figures for the brightness modification at the end. But how to go about that was a mystery. Then I thought about the various compositing modes available in a video editing application I use. Davinci Resolve offers a mode called “Add” which causes the frame to add its brightness to the frame below it. And after all, isn’t that exactly what stacking is? I mean, stacking as I understand it is two things, first, alignment and second, adding the brightness of the frames. It occurred to me that the star field was very steady and probably would do ok without any additional alignment at all. So, maybe Davinci Resolve could handle stacking 10 frames per frame so to speak. It was worth a shot.

I went back to the original frames and imported them all into Davinci Resolve. I then dragged all 100 raw 200ms frames onto the timeline. In Resolve, there are many functions turned on by default. I don’t know for certain, but I assume they all take up some amount of memory. Knowing what I was about to do would very likely tax my system, I turned off every additional feature except the one I needed, compositing. I then repeated the operation, copying all 100 frames to the layer above and offset them by one frame. This being layer 2 however, I selected all 100 frames, and changed the compositing mode to “ADD”. I copied this layer and did the same for layers 3 through 10 each time being careful to offset the new layer by 1 frame.

This procedure is summarized by the following diagram:

A Novel Approach to Processing Faint Image Sequences

Adding displaced raw frames to form 100 summed frames of 10 raw frames each (top row), using Davinci Resolve.

So, the first layer (bottom layer) had compositing set to normal, but every additional layer had compositing set to ADD. I had to wait several times while my system paused. I was sure it was going to crash at any moment. But luckily, it did not. I gave it a few minutes to settle and then hit play. There it was... right in the middle of the frame where Ted left it. Bullseye! And the occultation was very near the beginning of the sequence too.

A Novel Approach to Processing Faint Image Sequences

This was a great success and certainly a novel use for the application. But it does leave me asking one question about accuracy. I feel confident that the beginning of the disappearance was accurate, certainly within 1 frame, because the target star can be distinctly seen to take a step dimmer after a series of comparable brightness. But regarding the reappearance, if the star was undetectable in any single summed frame, then it seems unlikely that the first frame I see is the actual first frame in the reappearance. I would imagine it would have to be the second frame at least, or possibly third. So, I am forced to wonder whether the occultation might have ended earlier than I am able to detect. Would it be more accurate to go to the final frame of the reappearance, and then count 10 frames backwards from there? Clearly work remains in deciding how to best apply this approach.

In the end, all that time messing about in BASIC and Deep Sky Stacker was unnecessary. I was able to take the raw frames directly into Davinci Resolve. And the process of being able to play the sequence as a video allowed a greater contrast between the stars and the moving background noise. It was an honor to be able to help Ted Barnes confirm another successful occultation.

The evening Sky Map for July 2025 from skymaps.com.

Note: a nice interactive sky chart from Sky and Telescope may be found at the link <https://skyandtelescope.org/interactive-sky-chart/>

Astrophotography

Deep Sky: ARP 286

- Don Spong

This page shows ARP 286, consisting of the galaxies NGC 5566 (the large galaxy near the center), NGC 5560 (upper middle), and NGC 5569 (to the left of center). These galaxies are gravitationally interacting. NGC 5566 is a barred spiral galaxy in Virgo about 66 Mly away. It is about 150 kly in diameter, and was discovered in 1786 by William Herschel. These galaxies are in *Arp's Atlas of Peculiar Galaxies*, hence the name ARP 286.

Deep Sky: ARP 286

- Don Spong

I especially like to image the peculiar galaxies. The distorted spiral shape of NGC 5560 is caused by gravitational interactions with NGC 5569. This image was taken at TAO on the evening of June 20, and was formed by stacking 90 1-minute exposures. It was done with a Celestron 8" Edge HD with 0.7 focal length reducer and a Bader IR/UV filter. The mount was a ZWO AM5, and everything was controlled by an onboard ASI AIR computer in live stacking mode. The camera was a ZWO 533MCP Pro in Bin1 mode (3008x3008), cooled to about -20 degrees. Post processing was done with PixInsight and Adobe Lightroom. It was during this imaging session that the unusual satellite (airplane?) crossing occurred, as shown on Page Three Astronomy. That image was discarded prior to stacking.

Deep Sky: NGC 6675 & 6685

- John Barnes

Our Louisville, Ky ORION member John Barnes has been using his Seestar 50 to attempt to extract distant, faint galaxies, despite the challenges posed by his local Bortle 6-7 skies. Recently he was able to image two faint galaxies in Lyra, near Vega; these are NGC 6675 and 6685, shown below and on the following page. The large image is a 5 min image from 3 July 2025, timestamped 22:41 (Eastern). Two attempts to enhance these galaxies are shown below.

NGC 6675 is a type SAbc spiral, angular dimensions 1.8'x1.3', v-mag 12.5, redshift $z = 0.008322$, distance *ca.* 35 Mpc or 115 Mly.

NGC6685 is a much more distant type S0 elliptical, with angular dimensions 1.1'x0.9', v-mag 13.4, redshift $z = 0.021905$, distance *ca.* 95 Mpc or 310 Mly, which discovered by Edward Swift on 29 May 1887.

This information is primarily from Wikipedia and spider.seds.org.

Deep Sky: NGC 6675 & 6685

- John Barnes

Kevin provided six deep sky images taken recently at TAO using his SCT; I will present three here, and the remaining three in next month's Trapezium. Kevin's caption is given below each image.

NGC 3628, the Hamburger Galaxy, an edge-on spiral galaxy with a prominent dust band. Part of the Leo Triplet. Taken May 17. 20 x 1 minute exposures with UV-IR cutoff filter.

M97, the Owl Nebula (a planetary nebula). Taken on May 17 at TAO. Integration of 20 x 1 minute exposures with a UV-IR cutoff filter.

The Iris Nebula (C4), a reflection nebula in Cepheus. The nebula is lit by the newly formed star at its center. The nebula is blue because the star at the center is Class B, so it emits most of its light in the blue part of the spectrum. Integration of 45 x 1 minute exposures taken with a UV-IR cutoff filter. Taken June 21.

Appendices

Astronomy

- tb

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate.
Exact numerical relationships are indicated as such.

1 ly = 1 ly (Julian) = *exactly* 9 460 730 472 580. 8 km = 63 241. 077 084 ... AU
c = speed of light = *exactly* 299 792 458 m/s = *exactly* ☺ 1 ly/yr.
1 AU = *exactly* 149 597 870. 7 km
1 parsec (pc) = 3. 261 598 ... light years (ly)
1 yr (Julian) = *exactly* 365.25 d = *exactly* 31 557 600 s
1 d = *exactly* 86 400 s

distance to α Cen A = 1.346(2) pc = 4.390(8) ly
distance to the center of the galaxy ~ 8 kpc ~ 25 kly (considerable uncertainty)

1 nm = 1 nanometer = 10^{-9} m *exactly*
 H_{α} wavelength = 656.2 nm

+ 0.5 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{1/5}$ x fainter =	1. 584 893 ... x fainter
+ 1 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{2/5}$ x fainter =	2. 511 886 ... x fainter
+ 2 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{4/5}$ x fainter =	6. 309 ... x fainter
+ 2.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^1 x fainter =	10 x fainter
+ 3 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{6/5}$ x fainter =	15. 848 ... x fainter
+ 4 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{8/5}$ x fainter =	39. 810 ... x fainter
+ 5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^2 x fainter =	100 x fainter
+ 6 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{12/5}$ x fainter =	251. 188 ... x fainter
+ 7.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^3 x fainter =	1000 x fainter
+ 8 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{16/5}$ x fainter =	1584. 893 ... x fainter
+ 10 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^4 x fainter =	10 000 x fainter
+ 20 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^8 x fainter =	100 000 000 x fainter

Brightness is proportional to $1 / \text{distance}^2$

10 x more distant = *exactly* 10^2 x fainter = + 5 change in magnitude
 10^2 x more distant = *exactly* 10^4 x fainter = + 10 change in mag
 10^3 x more distant = *exactly* 10^6 x fainter = + 15 change in mag

Absolute magnitude M_{abs} is the brightness as seen from a distance of 10 pc
 M_{abs} (our sun) = 4.83

17th mag is about 1 optical photon / cm^2 s (Barnes's rule ☺)

Astronomy (cont.)

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate.
Exact numerical relationships are indicated as such.

R.A. = RA = Right Ascension = the angle ϕ around the celestial polar axis, usually quoted in hours, minutes, and seconds (*h m s*); analogous to longitude.

Dec = Declination = the angle θ above the celestial equator, usually quoted in degrees, minutes, and seconds ($^{\circ} \ ' \ ''$); analogous to latitude.

The RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles, together with a reference epoch such as J2000.0, specify an object's direction in the sky.

A unit length vector ("unit vector") $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ pointing towards an object in the sky ("on the celestial sphere") in terms of RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\eta} = \cos(\theta) \cos(\phi) \mathbf{x} + \cos(\theta) \sin(\phi) \mathbf{y} + \sin(\theta) \mathbf{z} = C(c \mathbf{x} + s \mathbf{y}) + S \mathbf{z}$$

The arc angle Θ_{12} between any two directions in the sky $\boldsymbol{\eta}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\eta}_2$ (or any two stars) using the dot product formula and some obvious abbreviations, satisfies

$$\cos(\Theta_{12}) = \sin(\theta_1)\sin(\theta_2) + \cos(\theta_1)\cos(\theta_2)\cos(\phi_1 - \phi_2) = S_1 S_2 + C_1 C_2 c_{1-2}$$

$$1 \text{ degree} = \pi/180 \text{ radians} = 1.745 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcmin} = \pi/10800 \text{ radians} = 2.909 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcsec} = 1 \text{ asec} = \pi/648000 \text{ radians} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ mas} = 10^{-3} \text{ asec} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 km} = 4.848 \text{ mm}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 AU} = 725.3 \text{ km}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 pc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

$$1 \text{ mas @ 1 kpc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

JD = Julian Date (Astronomer's calendar) = a simple count of days starting at noon UT on Monday 1 Jan 4713 BC. That date and time was the start of Julian Day 0. The current JD can be inferred from the value on the cover of the Trapezium.

The 80 Brightest Stars

The 80 brightest stars (c/o Wikipedia), and their distances from Earth in light years, the first 50 with errors (from Gaia data, or Simbad as an alternative).

1	Sirius	8.709	0.005	41	Menkalinan	7670	400
2	Canopus	309.	16.	42	Atria	390.6	7.0
3	alpha Centauri A	4.395	0.008	43	Alhena	109.3	8.2
4	Arcturus	36.7	0.2	44	Peacock	178.8	5.1
5	Vega	25.04	0.07	45	Alsephina	80.6	0.78
6	Capella	42.81	0.26	46	Mirzam	492.7	16.4
7	Rigel	863.	78.	47	Polaris	432.6	6.3
8	Procyon	11.46	0.05	48	Alphard	180.3	1.8
9	Archenar	139.4	3.4	49	Hamal	65.8	0.33
10	Betelgeuse	498.	63.	50	Diphda	96.3	0.46
11	beta Centauri	392.	24.	51	Mizar	97.8	
12	Altair	16.73	0.05	52	Nunki	227.8	
13	alpha Crucis	322.	16.	53	Menkent	58.8	000
14	Aldebaran	66.64	1.05	54	Alpheratz	97.0	000
15	Antares	554.	94.	55	Mirach	197.4	000
16	Spica	250.	13.	56	Rasalhague	48.6	000
17	Pollux	33.78	0.09	57	Algieba	130.1	000
18	Fomalhaut	25.13	0.09	58	Kochab	130.9	000
19	Deneb	1410	200	59	Saiph	647.1	000
20	Mimosa	279.	23.	60	Denebola	35.9	000
21	Regulus	79.30	0.67	61	Algol	94.0	000
22	Adhara	405.	7.0	62	Tiaki	177.0	000
23	Castor	50.68	0.032	63	Muhlifain	130.2	000
24	Shaula	571.2	7.5	64	Aspidiske	765.6	000
25	Gacrux	88.56	0.43	65	Suhail	544.5	000
26	Bellatrix	252.4	10.2	66	Alphecca	75.0	000
27	Elnath	133.9	1.9	67	Mintaka	692.5	000
28	Miaplacidus	113.2	0.43	68	Sadr	1832.3	000
29	Alnilam	1980	540	69	Eltanin	154.3	000
30	Regor	1120	110	70	Schedar	228.2	000
31	Alnair	101.0	0.66	71	Naos	1083.6	000
32	Alnitak	736.	106.	72	Almach	393.0	000
33	Alioth	82.55	0.42	73	Caph	54.7	000
34	Dubhe	122.9	2.2	74	Izar	235.8	000
35	Mirfak	506.	13.	75	alpha Lupi	464.6	000
36	Wezen	1610	300	76	epsilon Centauri	427.5	000
37	Sargas	300.	41.	77	Dschubba	491.2	000
38	Kaus Australis	143.3	1.5	78	Larawag	63.7	000
39	Avior	605.	47.	79	eta Centauri	305.7	000
40	Alkaid	103.9	0.79	80	Merak	79.7	000

Notable Star-Pair Angles

Notable star pairs (from the set of the 80 brightest stars listed above) that are close to a multiple of 5° separation. The angles are in degrees.

		Θ	$\Delta\theta$	defect (%)
Schedar	Caph	5	-0.085	1.7
Betelgeuse	Alnitak	10	0.017	0.17
Capella	Castor	30	-0.023	0.077
Procyon	Mirzam	30	-0.094	0.31
Elnath	Alnilam	30	-0.096	0.32
Alpheratz	Caph	30	0.060	0.20
Aldebaran	Pollux	45	0.013	0.029
Betelgeuse	Algol	50	-0.033	0.066
Alnitak	Naos	50	-0.049	0.098
Pollux	Alioth	60	0.065	0.11
Gacrux	Alphard	60	-0.001	0.002
Regulus	Bellatrix	70	-0.030	0.043
Sirius	Mirfak	80	-0.094	0.12
alpha_Centauri	Regulus	90	0.057	0.063
Vega	Denebola	90	-0.065	0.072
Fomalhaut	Caph	90	0.006	0.007
Deneb	Alnilam	120	0.059	0.049
Menkent	Mintaka	120	0.000	0.000
Sirius	Alphecca	135	-0.089	0.066
Aldebaran	Antares	170	-0.021	0.012

Exeunt

Here on this summer night in the grass and the lilac smell
drunk on the crickets and the starry sky
oh what fine stories we could tell
with this moonlight to tell them by.

A summer night, and you, and paradise,
So lovely and so full of grace,
Above your head, the universe has hung its lights,
And I reach out my hand to touch your face.

I believe in impulse, in all that is green,
Believe in the foolish vision that comes true,
Believe that all that is essential is unseen,
And for this lifetime I believe in you.

All of the lovers and the love they made:
Nothing that was between them was a mistake.
All that is done for love's sake,
Is not wasted and will never fade.

O love that shines from every star,
Love reflected in the silver moon;
It is not here, but it's not far.
Not yet, but it will be here soon.

A Love Poem
by Garrison Keillor

ORION and TAO (and Obed) General Information (links)

May be found at the following URLs:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tamke-Allan_Observatory

<http://www.orioninc.org/>

<https://orionastronomy.wordpress.com>

<https://www.facebook.com/ORIONAstronomyTN/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/454645124557215>

<https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tamke-Allan%20Observatory/120477734665841>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/?349-Tamke-Allan-Observatory>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/index.htm>

<https://twitter.com/TAOremote>

ORIONastronomy@groups.io

Where is TAO?

334 Caney Creek Rd, Rockwood, TN 37854

N 35° 49' 57", W 84° 37' 04"; Alt. 324 m

Where is Obed?

Lilly Bluff Overlook

N 36° 06' 09", W 84° 43' 17"; Alt. 402 m

Nemo Bridge (on the bridge, E bank of Emory River)

N 36° 04' 07", W 84° 39' 43"; Alt. 268 m

Trapezium back issues online, at CERN's zenodo database:

A full CERN zenodo doi url is for example <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8219253>;
a short form, *e.g.* zenodo.org/records/8219253, may also be used.

Vol. 49, Issue 4; Fri 15 Apr 2023:	zenodo.org/records/8219253
Vol. 49, Issue 5; Fri 12 May 2023:	8216818
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Vol. 50, Issue 11, Fri 15 Nov 2024:	14171218
Vol. 50, Issue 12, Fri 13 Dec 2024:	14394899
Vol. 51, Issue 01, Fri 10 Jan 2025:	14630165
Vol. 51, Issue 02, Fri 14 Feb 2025:	14873015
Vol. 51, Issue 03, Fri 14 Mar 2025:	15015954
Vol. 51, Issue 04, Fri 11 Apr 2025:	15200349
Vol. 51, Issue 05, Fri 16 May 2025:	15443035
Vol. 51, Issue 06, Fri 13 Jun 2025:	15660329
Vol. 51, Issue 07, Fri 11 Jul 2025:	15865574

Trapezium issues online, at CERN's zenodo database:

A generic link that lists Trapezium pdf issues (and other ORION documents) starting with the most recent, which does not require a specific zenodo document number, follows:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/rigel/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Fin du journal

According to my daughter Sietske, this image of “Big Kitty” Frannie as a kitten (27 July 2016) is from a time when Frannie was “so dense that light could not escape from her.” -Ed.